

Fitzroy-River-Martuarra. Photo by Jones

Opinion

Indigenous Water Rights

**STAND WITH MARTUWARRA
FITZROY RIVER FOR A FAIR GO!**

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Forty-three thousand (43,000) people from across the planet stood in solidarity with the Martuwarra Fitzroy River and signed petitions, many wrote submissions in response to the Western Australian (WA) government's, 'Discussion Paper' on water extraction from Martuwarra, Fitzroy River. The Martuwarra Fitzroy River Council worked closely with the WA Environmental Defenders Office and the Australian National University Water Justice Hub, eminent global scholars and practitioners, who spent considerable time, researching and comparing the two major submissions directed at water extraction within the Fitzroy River Catchment. The reports from these working groups were sent widely to diverse stakeholder groups, to share information, and draw attention to issues which require careful consideration. These submissions are not being made public and there are widespread concerns about the limitations of transparency and accountability to the greater public interests in this national and Aboriginal cultural heritage that is the Martuwarra, Fitzroy River.

Of particular concern is the lack of climate science, more importantly, how climate change is real and is now impacting the health and wellbeing of our Aboriginal people living in remote areas in the Country. Food insecurity and water

scarcity are real and many of the living water systems are being impacted and drying up. The seasonal calendars Aboriginal people rely on, are all out of balance. Aboriginal people are worried, and we hear the words of senior Elders now past, *'you came, you stole the land, you made us slaves, now you are back for the water, what is going to be left for blackfellas'*.

As Chair of the Council I have often stated that *'if we want to prevent ecocide and genocide it is time to redefine the dream of Northern Development, the dream must take notice of what the elders are saying'*. Senior Walmajarri Elder, Joe Brown, asks the hard questions, *'how come government think they own the water, they never been born alongside the river...if they drain the water out, that will kill the culture'*. Many believe without specific legislation for climate science, governance, and adaptive management of the Martuwarra, all they can see is foreseeable harm.

The Martuwarra Fitzroy River Council strongly believes that now is the moment in history to prevent a disaster. We need a statutory framework, with serious investment to bring everyone to the table to co-design any 'water plans' for this system. Hopefully, limnologists and

other water scientists and managers will unite with us to create a truly equitable water plan. Martuwarra Fitzroy River Council elders and their young leaders as guardians of the Martuwarra from the beginning of time, are clear, they support economic development and prosperity but it can't be business as usual *'after 150 years of invasive colonial development, it's time for justice and equity now, it is no longer about a water interest, it is about a water right. Importantly, our law of obligation is to protect Martuwarra now, for all generations to come'*.

Rivers are the lifeblood of all Nations, and rivers must be valued and respected, beyond seeing them as a 'resource' for the benefit of a few. Traditional Owners believe these cultural and environmental assets and capital are the catalyst to new and forever economies, published in the Martuwarra Fitzroy River Catchment Estate Conservation and Management Plan. We must all stand together globally, with our rivers to ensure our rivers have the right to life, to live and flow. Stand with with Martuwarra and stay connected with this sacred River, ancestral serpent being, see www.martuwarrafitzroyriver.org.

19th June 2021 River Country Photo by Lachie Carracher

Rosie and Grace Mulligan

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Some Publications

RiverOfLife M, Taylor KS, Poelina A. 2021. Living Waters, Law First: Nyikina and Mangala water governance in the Kimberley, Western Australia, Australasian Journal of Water Resources, DOI: 10.1080/13241583.2021.1880538

RiverOfLife M, Poelina A, Bagnall D, Li M. 2020. Recognizing the Mardoowarra's First Law Right to Life as a Living Ancestral Being. Special Edition: Indigenous Water Rights in Comparative Law, University of Canterbury School of Law, Christchurch (New Zealand).

O'Donnell E, Poelina A, Pelizzon A, Clark C. 2020. Stop burying the lede: the essential role of Indigenous law(s) in creating rights for nature. Special Edition: Indigenous Water Rights in Comparative Law, University of Canterbury School of Law, Christchurch (New Zealand).

RiverOfLife M, Poelina A, Alexandra J, Samnakay N. 2020. A Conservation and Management Plan for the National Heritage Listed Fitzroy River Catchment Estate (No.1). Fitzroy Crossing, Western Australia: Martuwarra Council. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3870606>

Poelina A, Taylor KS, Perdrisat I. 2019. Martuwarra Fitzroy River Council: An Indigenous cultural approach to collaborative water governance. Australasian Journal of Environmental Management 26: 236–254.

Lim M, Poelina A, Bagnall D. 2017. Can the Fitzroy River Declaration ensure the realisation of the First Laws of the River and secure sustainable and equitable futures for the West Kimberley? Australian Environment Review 32: 18–24.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5730003>

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